

Communicative Language Teaching (CLT): Implementation of role play in improving critical thinking in Senior High School

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Abstract:

One learning method that is effective in improving critical thinking among high school students is the CLT method. This method trains students to be able to apply learning materials to real-life contexts or everyday life. The combination of CLT and role play can make learning interesting and motivate students to learn. This study aims to determine how the implementation of role play improves critical thinking among high school students, as well as the role of teachers in this learning process. The role of students is not only to listen to instructions from teachers, but also to actively participate in classroom learning, while the role of teachers is to facilitate and supervise learning activities to ensure they run smoothly. This study uses a qualitative descriptive approach, such as data collection conducted through the identification of relevant topics from several journals from Google Scholar. An example of this activity is described using an implementation table, such as students listening to instructions from the teacher and forming groups, then beginning to analyze the news and discuss it with their group. Next, for assessment, students present in front of the class as news anchors, and other groups listen and take notes on the news or information that has been presented. The results of this learning activity show that students are able to analyze news, exchange information and ideas, and experience an increase in speaking, listening, writing, and reading skills. In role-play activities, students are trained to think critically and participate directly or actively in learning activities in the classroom. With regular practice, students will begin to get used to thinking critically, and their English skills will improve. These findings also reveal the extent of the teacher's influence in increasing student motivation to learn, such as how interesting the materials are and the activities designed for learning in the classroom.

Keywords: CLT, critical thinking, news anchor, role play, high school.

Introduction

In this era of globalization, with technology developing rapidly every day, English is often used as a means of communication on social media. Learning English is very important for students to prepare them for the future, so teachers have an important role to make learning interesting and effective. Speaking, listening, writing, and reading skills are essential in English language learning, with speaking being one of the most important skills. To master this skill, regular practice and confidence are needed, so English language learning requires the direct participation of students to learn and practice. Learning that only focuses on memorization

makes students lazy, bored, and less involved in learning. Learning must be made as effective as possible so that students understand and are able to implement the learning material in real life. Lack of practice often makes students less confident when speaking English, and students become passive, only listening to the teacher explain the material. In this case, the teachers were challenged because they have to develop their teaching methods or media in order to attract students' attention and motivation in learning English (Fitriana & Maro, 2018). The challenge faced by teachers is how to create effective learning that makes students active in the classroom.

One effective way to engage students in learning is to use the communicative language teaching method. By using this method, students are expected to be able to apply what they have learned in real life. CLT is an approach to language teaching methodology that emphasizes (1) authenticity, (2) interaction, (3) student-centered learning, (4) task-based activities, (5) communication for the real world, and (6) meaningful purposes (Darwanto et al., 2024). This approach uses communication as a learning tool, where speaking skills are essential. The objectives of the Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) method include enabling language to become a communication tool used by students and using language so that students can express themselves in communication (Inayah & Albar, 2021). One example of a learning activity using the CLT method is role play. Students play the role of a news anchor, so they actually practice the gestures and expressions of a news anchor. Through this, students will gain a better understanding through practice. From this practice, students' abilities will improve, such as critical thinking, confidence, and creativity.

Based on the research data, it was found that 21% of students had moderate critical thinking skills, 64% had low critical thinking skills, and 15% had very low critical thinking skills (Susilawati et al., 2020). These data show that most high school students in these schools have low critical thinking skills. A lack of critical thinking skills can cause students to become passive, lazy readers, easily give up, and have difficulty solving problems. Therefore, playing the role of a news anchor can improve students' critical thinking skills to learn to read, understand, identify, and filter information from various sources. This learning can also improve student collaboration, such as sharing information obtained with other friends to exchange information and analyze whether the news is true or not. In the process of analyzing information, students participate directly in sorting the news or information, questioning what issues are being discussed, and what solutions are appropriate to deal with these issues.

The CLT method is very effective in improving the critical thinking skills of high school students. The CLT learning method as a news anchor (role play) is a form of practical learning that focuses on student participation, which can foster their critical thinking skills. The communicative language teaching method provided teacher roles to make the class more responsible, namely: as the manager, counselor, facilitator, analyst, and motivator (Hati Laia SMA Negeri, 2024). The study mentions that 1. Teachers as managers, who prepare lessons by planning learning activities, 2. Teachers as counselors, who supervise student activities in the classroom and correct any mistakes, 3. Teachers as facilitators, who prepare learning media or tools, 4. Teachers as analysts, who analyze the learning activities (whether they are running properly and well), 5. Teachers as motivators, who give praise and motivation to students. Thus, teachers are no longer the source or center of information for students but rather facilitators who facilitate student learning activities. The role of students is to participate in learning activities in the classroom, be active in problem solving, be confident in their abilities, and cultivate a sense of curiosity so that their critical thinking skills improve. Teachers have an important role in the learning activities in the classroom; therefore, teachers try to come up with creative ideas or methods so that learning is not monotonous and is enjoyable.

Role-playing or acting as a news anchor can improve students' English skills, namely speaking, listening, writing, and reading. Students learn new vocabulary, become clear in their pronunciation, and gain confidence when playing the role of a news anchor, reading the news in front of the class (speaking skills). Students listen to and obtain information from the news delivered by their classmates (listening skills), and they also take notes on the information or news they obtain from their friends (writing skills). Before role-playing as news anchors, the teacher assigns students to read several news articles and analyze whether the news is true from various available sources (reading skills). In this learning activity, students are not only able to fulfill one of the 4 C competencies, namely critical thinking, but also all 4 C competencies (Critical Thinking, Collaboration, Communication, and Creativity). For example, students acquire critical thinking through analyzing the information or news they obtain, collaboration through exchanging information with friends and discussing it together. Communication is developed as students explain and convey information clearly, while creativity is fostered through the style of delivery and language used. The following is an example of the implementation of role-playing as a news anchor in high school, analyzed based on the researcher's learning experience and literature.

STAGES	ACTIVITIES	STUDENT ROLE	STUDENTS ENGLISH SKILLS	CRITICAL THINKING ASPECTS THAT ARE DEVELOPED
1. Preparation	Teachers divide students into groups, introduce role play, and explain the activities to be carried out.	Listen to the teacher's instructions.	Listening skill	Understanding what the teacher says.
2. Analysis	The teacher assigned students to find news articles and analysis them by distinguishing whether the news was factual or opinion-based. For example: News about health, drinking coffee every day, what happens to the body?	Students search for news from various sources and analyze it.	Reading skill	Analyzing whether the news is true or not.
3. Discussion	The teacher instructs students to discuss with their group members.	Students are discussing.	Speaking & writing skills	Collaboration, exchanging information or ideas.

4. Practice	The teacher gives examples of how a news anchor delivers the news.	Students practice what the teacher has taught them.	Speaking & listening skills	Implementation of role play.
5. Assessment	The teacher selects a group to present in front of the class and instructs the other groups to listen and take notes on what has been said.	Students practiced with their groups in front of the class while the others took notes on the information they learned.	Speaking & listening skills	Analyze the news, and understand what your friends from other groups are saying.

The purpose of this study is to analyze the implementation of role play in improving students' critical thinking skills. This study also aims to identify student learning activities, such as what roles they play in participating directly in learning and what skills they use. In addition to focusing on the role of students, this study also focuses on the role of teachers in classroom learning.

Problem Statement

This problem formulation focuses on how role play is implemented in high schools using the CLT (Communicative Language Teaching) method to improve one of the 4 Cs competencies, namely critical thinking. This study also identifies what abilities or skills students will acquire through role play, as well as the role of teachers in ensuring that learning activities run smoothly. This study aims to identify the obstacles students face in learning, such as why students often get bored and inactive during classroom learning. Thus, it is important to assess the effectiveness of role play learning to find out how students can improve their English skills and critical thinking abilities.

Research Method

This article was written using a qualitative descriptive approach by analyzing and collecting topics from various sources related to the Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) method in English language learning, the implementation of role play to improve critical thinking in high school students, and the author's experiences with learning activities carried out in high school. The author analyzed the data using content analysis, namely by identifying the content of various journals and linking it to examples of role play implementation as news anchors related to English language skills and critical thinking development. The ability to think critically helps individuals to face challenges in the future in many different aspects, such as social, cultural, and economic (Maro et al., 2013). So, thinking critically is very helpful for students in preparing for their future. The application of the Communicative Language Teaching/CLT method is an effective learning method that can foster students' enthusiasm for learning English (Derojat et al., 2025). In this study, there were significant results, namely that students' enthusiasm for learning increased by using the CLT learning method.

This study was designed to determine the effectiveness of role-playing in English learning in high school. The steps in the literature study in this research were: first, collecting and reading materials or topics to be studied; second, analyzing the material; third, citing material related to the topic; and finally, processing the material from the research results.

Results and Discussion

Based on a literature review of several journals and articles, the results of this study show that the implementation of role play can improve students' critical thinking skills, English language skills, and enthusiasm for learning. Role play can also train students to communicate in real-life contexts, encourage student engagement, and develop students' potential. Role play creates an enthusiastic learning atmosphere in every meeting, and students involved in the learning process can freely express themselves in their roles and create attributes in each performance to support the learning process (Wahyuni et al., 2018). In this case, students quickly and easily understand the learning material. An example of learning activities using the CLT and role play methods is shown in the implementation table above, which contains 5 stages of activities that demonstrate an increase in students' critical thinking skills and English language skills. In the first stage, preparation, students are able to understand what the teacher says. In the second stage, analysis, students are able to distinguish between news containing

facts or opinions. In the third stage, discussion, students are able to collaborate with their groupmates and share news or information they have obtained. In the fourth stage, practice, students are able to practice and communicate directly in class, in the fifth stage, assessment, students are able to capture the information conveyed by their friends during the presentation and record any news they have obtained. This activity trains students to think critically, such as analyzing the truth of information or news, working together to discuss material, and freely expressing their opinions. This activity also improves their English skills, such as listening, reading, speaking, and writing. CLT has implied new roles for teachers and students (Quraishah et al., 2022). The role of teachers in this learning activity is as facilitators who provide tools and materials for learning activities and also as supervisors to oversee the learning activities in the classroom to run smoothly. Meanwhile, the role of students in this learning activity is to participate and follow all learning activities in the classroom.

Effective learning strategies will influence students' understanding and learning outcomes (Sutena, 2023). This means that students' success in learning is influenced by how effective teachers are in creating learning materials or activities in the classroom. If teachers are well-trained in the CLT approach and if teachers and learners play their proper roles imposed by the CLT curriculum, the concept of the CLT approach will be successfully implemented (Nayeen et al., 2020). The CLT approach concept will be successfully implemented if teachers and students carry it out according to their respective roles. From this, it can be concluded that the roles of students and teachers are important in ensuring the success of learning activities. The emphasis on meaningful, context-based communication, interactive learning, and student-centered approaches in CLT has fostered a more engaging and effective language learning experience (Lestari & Margana, 2024). The implementation of CLT can make learning more interesting, and when combined with role play, learning becomes more interactive and students gain learning experiences in real contexts.

Conclusion

CLT is a communicative learning method that encourages students to actively learn in class. The role of the teacher as a facilitator who creates, provides, and supervises student activities plays an important role in how smoothly and successfully the learning process takes place. Role-playing as a news anchor is one example of interactive learning that can improve students' speaking, listening, reading, and writing skills. In addition, students are also trained to continue thinking critically, such as analyzing and solving problems. Overall, the

implementation of role-playing is very influential in improving critical thinking among high school students. Role play trains students to learn in a real-world context, so that students become accustomed to expressing themselves and become more enthusiastic when learning in class. The lack of student motivation to learn English is due to students not being active in classroom learning and also to learning that is uninteresting or monotonous. Therefore, the role of teachers in designing or creating learning materials is very influential in determining whether or not the learning is interesting. CLT and role play are the right combination to foster student motivation and develop their critical thinking skills.

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